

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BABAFEMI****FIRST NAME: LUCY****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord for Mac version 16.77.1)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The structure of an essay should be in the following format:

- Introduction, body, and conclusion.**¹
- Body, introduction, and conclusion.
- Analysis, introduction, and conclusion.
- Acknowledgment, introduction, and conclusion.

2. An apostrophe is used to indicate one of the following:

- Missing letters in a word.**²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

² *Ibid.*, 17.

- Missing words in a sentence.
 - Punctuations in a sentence.
 - A word in a plural form.
3. What sources are considered secondary sources in research?
- Articles, papers, books, and reports.**³
 - Books, papers, diaries, and reports.
 - Articles, papers, maps, and books.
 - Reports, books, articles, and letters
4. What is the correct format for citing a letter in notes?
- Name of sender, name of recipient, and date of correspondence.**⁴
 - Date of correspondence, name of recipient, and name of sender.
 - Date of correspondence, name of sender, and name of recipient.
 - Date of correspondence and name of sender.
5. What are the significant components of dissertation research?
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, dissertation manuscript.**⁵

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018) 36.

⁴ Ibid., 188.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017) 9.

- Dissertation analysis, dissertation question, dissertation concept paper, manuscript.
- Dissertation analysis, dissertation prospectus, dissertation concept paper, manuscript.
- Dissertation, dissertation analysis, dissertation prospectus, manuscript.

6. Which of the following factors contribute to successful dissertation research?

All of the above⁶

- Good planning.
- Good communication.
- An effective working process.

7. What is the most essential aspect of research?

The research questions.⁷

- The statement of the problem.
- The abstract.
- The research data.

8. The *Acquis*, which is the body of EU law, comprises all of the following except:

Primary legislation.⁸

- The case law of the Court of Justice.

⁶ Ibid., 22.

⁷ Ibid., 35.

⁸ Tim Cooper et al., *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eight Edition (European Union, 2021), 74.

- The declarations and resolutions adopted by the EU.
- Measures relating to justice and home affairs.

9. When was the European Union Court of Justice established originally?

1952.⁹

1962.

1942.

1982.

10. How many countries make up the European Union?

27 countries.¹⁰

37 countries.

26 countries.

37 countries.

⁹ Ibid., 90.

¹⁰ Ibid., 98.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. Ninth Edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.